

Multiplier Waveform Inversion: Time-Domain Application with Adaptive Step-Length

Atefeh Rahimi¹, Kamal Aghazade², Ali Gholami¹ and Hamidreza Siahkoobi¹

¹ *Institute of Geophysics, University of Tehran, Tehran, Iran*

² *Institute of Geophysics, Polish Academy of Sciences, Warsaw, Poland*

ABSTRACT

Time-domain full waveform inversion (FWI) is appropriate for large-scale problems, with the general multivariate formulation to seek for model parameters and seismic wavefield by minimizing an appropriate regularization function while adhering to the wave equation and observation equation constraints. The classic FWI addresses the problem in the frame of reduced search space through eliminating the wavefield from the optimization parameters and then applying the quadratic penalty function to the resulting mono-variate problem. This conventional strategy suffers from illconditioning, slow convergence rate, and local minima trap in the lack of an appropriate starting model. To address these issues, we propose using the augmented Lagrangian function in the frame of the method of multiplier rather than the penalty function. This multiplier waveform inversion (MWI) modifies the data residual of the standard FWI with the Lagrange multiplier that is computed by the running sum of data residuals during iterations. This modification aids in fitting the data in a stable manner in the absence of a good initial model without incurring additional computation costs that results in a faster convergence rate and more accurate models. Two synthetic numerical examples are provided to show the effectiveness of the suggested strategy.

KEYWORDS: *FWI, MWI, LAGRANGE MULTIPLIERS, CONSTRAINED OPTIMIZATION, SEISMIC IMAGING.*

1- INTRODUCTION

Within the domain of seismic imaging, full waveform inversion (FWI) is a widely employed technique to characterize the physical attributes of subsurface. The procedure involves utilizing an optimization framework to determine the model parameters that can accurately reproduce the observed data (Virieux et al., 2017). From a mathematical standpoint, FWI is a nonlinearly constrained optimization problem. The conventional approach to solving it is to employ the quadratic penalty function (e.g., Guitton, 2012). However, the penalty-based FWI demonstrates certain limitations, including ill-conditioning, sensitivity to the initial model, challenges in determining the optimum effective penalty parameter or step length, and a slow convergence rate when the Hessian matrix is not taken into account (Métivier et al., 2017). Therefore enhancing the resilience of FWI with respect to the initial model become an active area of research. This includes, e.g., methods based on enlarging the inversion's search space (see Operto et al., 2023, and references therein), or modification of the misfit function (Pladys et al., 2017).

The approach introduced in this paper diverges from conventional methods by addressing the standard ℓ_2 misfit function through an alternative optimization algorithm—the method of multipliers, also recognized as the augmented Lagrangian method (Powell, 1969). By employing this method, we preserve the computational efficiency of the standard algorithm, including aspects of memory usage and computational complexity, while enhancing robustness (Gholami, 2023). The resulting methodology, termed Multiplier Waveform Inversion (MWI), substitutes the traditional penalty objective function with an associated augmented Lagrangian function. This transformation gives rise to a saddle point problem characterized by the alternating minimization and maximization of the augmented Lagrangian function concerning the model parameter and the Lagrange multiplier, respectively. Importantly, these Lagrange multipliers are defined in the data space, mitigating concerns related to excessive memory usage. The use of data-side multipliers in the standard FWI captures the nonlinearity of the data associated with high-order scattering which are not predicted by the linearized forward operator. This allows us to correct the data residual before being used as the adjoint source for computing the back propagated wavefields. These multipliers correlate to the multiscattered component of the scattered wavefield, so assisting in accurately matching the multiscattered portion of the data.

Gholami et al. (2023), tested the performance of the MWI using frequency domain formulation. Here, we extend the MWI approach to time-domain. Although, frequency-domain FWI benefits from multishot simulation through use of direct

solvers, in contrast, the time domain formulation is better suited for large scale problems and has the advantage of applying temporal windowing to data, enabling the selection of certain arrivals based on time.

2- THEORY

We make the assumption of a constant density acoustic approximation. Assuming this condition, the medium is characterized by the wave-speed (\mathbf{c}). The collected data, denoted as \mathbf{d} , is obtained by sampling the seismic wavefield, represented as \mathbf{u} , which is generated by the source term \mathbf{b} . The forward problem includes solving the wave equation $\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{m})\mathbf{u} = \mathbf{b}$, where $\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{m}) = \mathbf{m} \circ \partial_{tt} - \Delta$ represents the discretized wave equation operator with appropriate boundary condition, and $\mathbf{m} = \mathbf{c}^{-2}$ (squared slowness). In the context of FWI, the model estimation problem is formulated as a nonlinearly constrained optimization problem. It entails minimizing a general regularization term while ensuring fidelity to the observed data (Gholami et al., 2023):

$$\underset{\mathbf{m}}{\text{minimize}} \mathcal{R}(\mathbf{m}) \text{ subject to } \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{m}) = \mathbf{d}. \quad (1)$$

Where, $\mathcal{R}(\mathbf{m})$ refers to a suitable regularization function, the forward operator is symbolized by the expression $\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{m}) = \mathbf{P}\mathbf{A}^{-1}(\mathbf{m})\mathbf{b}$, and \mathbf{P} is responsible for sampling the wavefield at receiver locations. In order to address (1), two general approaches can be used, which involve replacing the constrained problem with a series of unconstrained subproblems (Nocedal and Wright, 2006). The primary method offers the use of a quadratic penalty function, a frequently used approach in classical FWI (e.g., Guitton, 2012):

$$\underset{\mathbf{m}}{\text{minimize}} \mathcal{R}(\mathbf{m}) + \frac{\mu}{2} \|\delta\mathbf{d}(\mathbf{m})\|_2^2, \quad (2)$$

where $\delta\mathbf{d}(\mathbf{m}) = \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{m}) - \mathbf{d}$, and $\mu \in \mathbb{R}^+$ is the penalty parameter. As an alternative approach, we propose utilization of the method of multipliers (Powell, 1969), which replaces the constrained problem with the associated augmented Lagrangian function as:

$$\underset{\mathbf{m}}{\text{min}} \underset{\boldsymbol{\lambda}}{\text{max}} \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{m}, \boldsymbol{\lambda}) = \mathcal{R}(\mathbf{m}) + \langle \boldsymbol{\lambda}, \delta\mathbf{d}(\mathbf{m}) \rangle_{t,x} + \frac{\mu}{2} \|\delta\mathbf{d}(\mathbf{m})\|_2^2. \quad (3)$$

Here, $\boldsymbol{\lambda}$ represents the Lagrange multiplier, and $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle_{t,x}$ denotes the inner product that involves integration over both time and space. The solution of equation (3) is as a saddle point. This means that the objective function achieves a minimum along the direction of the model parameters, \mathbf{m} , and a maximum along the direction of the Lagrange multipliers, $\boldsymbol{\lambda}$. Consequently, this multiplier waveform inversion (MWI) involves an iterative framework, wherein model estimation and Lagrange multiplier updates are performed alternately in a two-step recursive algorithm (see Gholami et al., 2023, for details)

$$\mathbf{m}^+ = \underset{\mathbf{m}}{\text{argmin}} \mathcal{R}(\mathbf{m}) + \frac{\mu}{2} \|\tilde{\boldsymbol{\lambda}} + \delta\mathbf{d}(\mathbf{m})\|_2^2 \quad (4a)$$

$$\tilde{\boldsymbol{\lambda}}^+ = \tilde{\boldsymbol{\lambda}} + \delta\mathbf{d}(\mathbf{m}^+), \quad (4b)$$

where $\tilde{\boldsymbol{\lambda}} = \frac{\boldsymbol{\lambda}}{\mu}$. Here we denote the background values of the variables without indices, while the updated variables are denoted by a superscript “+”. The model update in (4a) can be achieved through the following gradient descent step:

$$\mathbf{m}^+ = \mathbf{m} - \alpha \delta\mathbf{m} \quad (5)$$

where $\delta\mathbf{m} = \mathbf{H}^{-1} \mathbf{g}$ is the model perturbation, wherein \mathbf{H} denotes appropriate preconditioner or Hessian matrix, and \mathbf{g} is the gradient vector. The step-length α can be approximately obtained by (Pica et al., 1990):

$$\alpha = \frac{(\mathbf{J}\delta\mathbf{m})^T \delta\mathbf{d}^*(\mathbf{m})}{(\mathbf{J}\delta\mathbf{m})^T (\mathbf{J}\delta\mathbf{m})}, \quad (6)$$

where $\mathbf{J} = \nabla_{\mathbf{m}} \delta\mathbf{d}(\mathbf{m})$ is the Jacobian matrix, and $\delta\mathbf{d}^*(\mathbf{m}) = \tilde{\boldsymbol{\lambda}} + \delta\mathbf{d}(\mathbf{m})$. Of note, for the classical FWI method,

$\delta \mathbf{d}^*(\mathbf{m}) = \delta \mathbf{d}(\mathbf{m})$. Upon comparing equation (2) with equation (4a), it becomes evident that the model estimation subproblem of FWI and MWI and specifically their gradient terms differ solely in the Lagrange multiplier, $\tilde{\lambda}$. This multiplier vector shifts the data residuals, ensuring that the minimizer of the penalty function matches the desired minimizer of the constrained problem, even for a moderate value of the penalty. Gholami et al. (2023) demonstrated that the Lagrange multiplier serves as an estimate for the multiscattered component of the scattered wavefield, aiding in a better linearization of the problem and making the inversion well-posed. The MWI approach only stores running sum of the data residuals during iterations (subproblem 4b) without significant computational cost and memory burden compared to the classical FWI.

3- NUMERICAL RESULTS

We assess the efficacy of MWI in contrast to the classic FWI, where FWI is performed using the same setup as MWI but with a zero multiplier vector. In the first example, we examine a simple velocity model depicted in Fig. 1a, with dimensions of 1 km by 1.5 km, discretized with a grid spacing of 10 m. The surface acquisition is conducted using 6 sources, employing a Ricker wavelet with a dominating frequency of 15 Hz. Additionally, there are 75 receivers uniformly distributed on the surface. The entire duration of the recording is set to be 3 sec, with a sample period of 1 ms. The FWI and MWI techniques are utilized to reconstruct the velocity model, beginning with the model shown in Fig. 1b. The results of the inversion, obtained after 200 iterations, are displayed in Fig. 1c (for FWI) and Fig. 1d (for MWI). The classic FWI has converged to a local minimum. Only the layer boundaries are recovered using reflection data. On the other hand, the MWI technique has reconstructed the model reasonably good, exhibiting improved precision in distinguishing all layers. This observation is confirmed by the extracted velocity logs (Fig. 2a) and the computed data misfit term during the iteration process (Fig. 2b).

Figure 1: (a) True velocity. (b) Initial velocity. (c and d) Inversion results obtained by FWI (c) and MWI (d).

For the second example, the highly challenging Camembert transmission test is considered. The subsurface velocity model consists of a circular anomaly with a velocity of 4.6 km/s, surrounded by a homogeneous background with a velocity of 4.0 km/s (Fig. 3a). The model has dimensions of 4.8 km by 6 km with grid spacing of 35.5 m. The acquisition is performed using 13 sources, specifically Ricker wavelets with a dominating frequency of 10 Hz, positioned on the top of the model, and 170 receivers evenly distributed on the bottom side of the model. Total recording time is 3 seconds with sampling rate of 1 ms. The inversion stage is initiated using the background model, which results in cycle skipping. The final estimated models for the FWI and MWI approaches after 200 iterations are displayed in Fig. 3(b)-(c), respectively.

Figure 2: (a) The extracted velocity logs from true, initial and estimated models. (b) The evolution of misfit function for FWI and MWI methods.

Figure 3: Camembert test. (a) True velocity. Inversion results obtained by time-domain FWI (b), timedomain MWI (c) and frequency-domain MWI (d) (Gholami et al., 2023). (e) True seismogram for the indicated source location in (a). Sample data residual at final iteration for (f) time-domain FWI, (g) time-domain MWI, and (h) frequency-domain MWI.

Figure 4: Camembert test. The evolution of misfit function for FWI and MWI methods .

failed to recover the model. On the other hand, the MWI approach in both time and frequency-domains overcame the deficiency of FWI and successfully reconstructed the model. The difference between seismogram computed at true model (Fig. 3e) and seismograms computed at the inversion results are shown in Fig. 3(f) (for time-domain FWI), Fig. 3(g) (for time-domain MWI) and Fig. 3(h) (for frequencydomain MWI). The computed data misfit term versus iteration is shown in Fig. 4. A slightly better data fit is obtained by time-domain MWI, which is due to full band inversion and optimal calculation of step-length during iterations.

4- CONCLUSTIONS

In this study, we tackled the challenges related to reduced search space classic FWI by utilizing the method of multipliers. This approach benefits from the use of multipliers that modifies the data misfit term, which helps to better fit the data and results in a higher quality models. The robustness of the proposed method is verified by synthetic examples.

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